

ADDRESSING DATA SCARCITY IN DEEP LEARNING-BASED PLANT DISEASE DETECTION USING GAN-BASED SYNTHETIC DATA AUGMENTATION

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Abstract

Early detection of plant diseases is critically important for preserving agricultural productivity and ensuring food security. Image processing and deep learning techniques can provide faster, more objective, and consistent results compared to human visual assessments in this field. However, the success of deep learning models largely depends on the availability of large and balanced datasets. In this study, a deep neural network based on the ResNet architecture was trained using an enriched image dataset, which was augmented via LeafGAN for the purpose of plant leaf disease detection.

To overcome the limitations of the original dataset, such as data imbalance and insufficient sample size, the LeafGAN model was first trained to generate synthetic leaf images that represent plant diseases. These synthetic images were then combined with the original dataset to create a more balanced and diverse training set. Subsequently, a model was developed based

on the ResNet architecture and trained using this dataset. The impact of the applied data augmentation method on model performance was thoroughly analyzed.

The results show that the dataset augmented with LeafGAN significantly improves classification accuracy. This study demonstrates that GAN-based data generation provides a practical and effective solution for training deep learning models with agricultural images. It also offers a valuable methodology for enhancing model performance in other domains facing data scarcity challenges.

Keywords: Smart farming, Precision agriculture, Plant disease detection, Deep learning

Özet

Bitki hastalıklarının erken tespiti, tarımsal verimliliğin korunması ve gıda güvenliğinin sağlanması açısından büyük önem taşımaktadır. Görüntü işleme ve derin öğrenme teknikleri, bu alanda insan gözüyle yapılan değerlendirmelere kıyasla daha hızlı, nesnel ve tutarlı sonuçlar sunabilmektedir. Derin öğrenme modellerinin başarısı büyük ölçüde geniş ve dengeli veri kümelerine bağlıdır ancak mevcut veri tabanları oldukça sınırlıdır. Bu çalışmada, bitki yapraklarındaki hastalıkların tespiti amacıyla, veri artırma yöntemi olarak LeafGAN kullanılarak zenginleştirilmiş bir görüntü veri kümesi oluşturulmuş ve ResNet tabanlı derin sinir ağları eğitilmiştir.

Çalışma kapsamında öncelikle, veri dengesizliği ve yetersiz örnek sayısı nedeniyle gerçek veri kümesinin sınırlayıcı etkilerini aşmak için LeafGAN modeli eğitilmiş ve bitki hastalığını temsil eden sentetik yaprak görüntüleri üretilmiştir. Bu sentetik görüntüler, orijinal veri kümesiyle birleştirilerek daha dengeli ve çeşitli bir eğitim seti elde edilmiştir. Ardından, ResNet mimarisi üzerine bir model geliştirilerek bu verilerle eğitilmiş ve uygulanan veri artırma yönteminin model performansı üzerindeki etkisi analiz edilmiştir.

Elde edilen sonuçlar, LeafGAN ile artırılan veri kümesinin, sınıflandırma doğruluğunu anlamlı ölçüde artırdığını göstermektedir. Bu çalışma, GAN tabanlı veri üretiminin tarımsal görüntülerle derin öğrenme modeli eğitimlerinde pratik ve etkili bir çözüm sunduğunu ortaya koymakta; aynı zamanda benzer alanlardaki düşük veri senaryolarında da derin öğrenme modellerinin başarımını artırmaya yönelik önemli bir çözüm sağlamaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Akıllı tarım, Hassas tarım, Bitki hastalığı tespiti, Derin öğrenme

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1. Introduction

Effectively identifying plant diseases is crucial for maintaining crop yields and ensuring food security. In recent years, deep learning models trained on large collections of images have shown great potential for this task. One of the most commonly used datasets is PlantVillage, which has enabled high-accuracy models, but these models often struggle when exposed to real-world, uncontrolled environments. This is mainly because datasets like PlantVillage lack the diversity needed to reflect the complexity of natural farming conditions (Jelali, 2024).

Most previous research in this space has leaned heavily on established deep learning architectures like AlexNet, VGG (Visual Geometry Group), GoogLeNet, ResNet. These models have achieved accuracy rates above 99% on PlantVillage data (Mohanty et al, 2016 – Ferenitos, 2018). But such results are misleading because they cannot show the same performance in the field. Real-world conditions introduce variability that these clean, well-labeled datasets not include. Additionally, problems like class imbalance and small sample sizes further limit how well these models perform outside the lab conditions (Barbedo, 2018).

To tackle these issues, our work explores the use of LeafGAN, a generative adversarial network designed specifically for plant leaf images, producing realistic image-to-image transformations from health to nonhealthy or vice versa. We apply LeafGAN to expand and balance the PlantVillage dataset by generating synthetic images that reflect more varied and realistic disease patterns. Using this enriched dataset, we train a ResNet-18 model from the ground up and compare its performance to a baseline model trained with Plantvillage dataset without LeafGAN augmentation.

2. Related Work

There's already a solid body of work demonstrating the effectiveness of deep learning for diagnosing plant diseases. For example, studies by Mohanty et al. and Ferenitos used models like AlexNet, GoogLeNet, and VGG to train classifiers using the PlantVillage dataset, reached accuracy levels more than 99% (Mohanty et al, 201 - Ferenitos, 2018). But, researchers like

Barbedo have raised valid concerns about relying too heavily on such datasets. The main concern is, data is captured under ideal conditions and does not represent the unpredictable nature of actual farming environments (Barbedo, 2018).

In response, researchers have started exploring generative methods, especially GANs, as a way to overcome data limitations. One promising approach is LeafGAN (Qin et al., 2020), which introduces synthetic variation by turning healthy leaves into realistic diseased ones using attention-based generation and segmentation-aware learning. LeafGAN has already been applied successfully to crops like cucumber, and its flexibility suggests it could be a valuable tool for boosting data diversity in agriculture, especially where real-world disease images are scarce.

3. Methodology

3.1 Dataset

We worked with a binary-labeled version of the PlantVillage dataset, which categorizes randomly selected plant leaf images into healthy and non-healthy classes. However, this dataset presents two major challenges: the classes are imbalanced, and there's limited variation within each category. As a result, models trained solely on this data risk overfitting and often fail to perform well when exposed to new, unseen conditions. To address these limitations, we used LeafGAN-based data augmentation approach. We collected real life healthy plant leaf images from the web and used them to generate realistic synthetic images of diseased leaves, we aimed to both balance the dataset and increase its diversity, ultimately helping the model learn more robust and generalizable features. Then we used healthy PlantVillage images to generate more diseased images using LeafGAN to build a new augmented dataset.

3.2 LeafGAN Architecture and Training Procedure

LeafGAN is an attention-guided generative adversarial network designed to convert healthy leaf images into diseased versions, simulating a wide range of plant disease appearances. The model is built around two key components: a generator that learns how to realistically overlay disease symptoms onto healthy leaves, and a discriminator that evaluates the quality and realism of these synthesized images (Figure 1). To make sure the disease transformations stay localized and don't distort the background, LeafGAN also incorporates a segmentation-guided attention mechanism known as LFLSeg. This module ensures that changes occur only within the leaf area, keeping the rest of the image intact.

Figure 2. GAN architecture

The training process relied on paired healthy and diseased images from the PlantVillage dataset. LeafGAN was optimized using a combination of standard GAN losses (adversarial loss, cycle-consistency loss, identity loss) as well as an auxiliary attention loss that sharpens the model's focus on disease-specific regions. Training was performed using the Adam optimizer. It began with a fixed learning rate phase lasting 10 epochs (--niter 10), followed by a linear learning rate decay over another 10 epochs (--niter_decay 10), summing up to 20 epochs in total. Throughout training, periodic visualizations and model checkpointing were used to monitor progress and save results.

Figure 2. Original healthy leaves (left) and LeafGAN generated diseased images (right)

Once training was complete, LeafGAN was used to generate a large number of synthetic diseased images by transforming healthy leaf samples. These synthetic images retained the original leaf structure while introducing realistic disease symptoms that varied in location, severity, and pattern (Figure 2). By enriching the dataset with these diverse samples, LeafGAN helped improve the robustness and generalization capabilities of previous plant disease detection models in more variable conditions.

3.3 Model Architecture and Training

For classification, we used the ResNet-18 architecture. To isolate and evaluate the effect of our data augmentation strategy, the model was trained from scratch, without using any pretrained weights. ResNet-18 consists of 18 convolutional layers with residual connections (Figure 3), which help stabilize training by addressing vanishing gradient issues common in deeper networks.

Figure 3. Resnet18 architecture

Training Specifications:

The input image size was 224×224 pixels. To improve model generalization, several data augmentation techniques were applied, including random resized cropping, random horizontal flipping, random rotations within ±15 degrees, and color jittering to vary brightness, contrast, and saturation. The model was trained using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.0001. Cross-entropy loss was used as the objective function, with a batch size of 32 and a total of 20 training epochs.

Model is trained in a GPU-accelerated environment with CUDA support. Throughout the training process, we monitored performance using a range of metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score to gain a comprehensive view of the model's behavior.

3.4 Evaluation Protocol

We tested both the baseline and the LeafGAN-augmented models on a separate subset of the PlantVillage dataset to unveil the generalization of the model by using random types of plant leaves that was never used-in-training.

4. Results

The ResNet-18 model trained with LeafGAN-augmented data outperformed the baseline across nearly all evaluation metrics. Although there was a slight drop in recall for the healthy class, the overall accuracy improved notably especially in detecting diseased leaves. This performance boost highlights the effectiveness of using GAN-generated images to tackle class imbalance and enhance intra-class variability, leading to more robust and generalizable models.

Table 1. Performance results

Metric	Baseline (PlantVillage Only)	Augmented (PlantVillage + LeafGAN)
Accuracy	0.506	0.775
Precision (Healthy)	0.33	0.48
Recall (Healthy)	0.69	0.62
F1-score (Healthy)	0.45	0.54
Precision (Nonhealthy)	0.77	0.89
Recall (Nonhealthy)	0.43	0.82
F1-score (Nonhealthy)	0.55	0.85
Macro F1-score	0.50	0.70
Weighted F1-score	0.52	0.78

5. Conclusion

This study highlights how GAN-based data augmentation can significantly enhance the performance of deep learning models in agricultural image classification. By using synthetic diseased leaf images generated through LeafGAN in the training, we achieved notable improvements using a relatively simple ResNet-18 deep neural network. These findings show the value of dataset diversity and demonstrate the potential of generative models to overcome limitations of data scarcity. Overall, this augmentation strategy offers a scalable and practical solution not just for plant disease detection, also for a wide range of image classification tasks where collecting large, diverse datasets is hard.

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